

INNOVADE: Digital Democracy for a Changing World

A new European initiative to make online civic participation secure, inclusive and effective.

Brussels, 28 January 2025 – INNOVADE (<https://innovade-democracy.eu/>) is a new EU-funded, 36-month project under HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01, dedicated to ensuring that digital democracy is transparent, accessible, and legally sound. As digital platforms become central to civic engagement, governments need robust policies and secure digital tools to prevent fragmentation, misinformation and digital exclusion.

The INNOVADE project officially launched in January 2025 with its Kick-Off Meeting in Brussels, bringing together a multidisciplinary consortium of experts in digital governance, AI, cybersecurity, legal compliance, and civic participation.

A Secure and Inclusive Digital Democracy

INNOVADE will provide governments, policymakers and civil society with the tools to strengthen democratic participation. The project will analyse digital democracy trends, assess risks and develop best practices, while also delivering a GDPR-compliant, AI-powered Digital Democracy App. This tool will enable secure and meaningful public decision-making, ensuring equal participation for all citizens, regardless of socio-economic background or digital literacy.

Real-World Testing Through Living Labs

To ensure practical and scalable solutions, INNOVADE is implementing a Living Labs approach, where citizens, policymakers, and technology experts will co-develop and test digital democracy tools in real-world settings. Pilots in [Geel \(Belgium\)](#) and [San Martín de la Vega \(Spain\)](#) will evaluate how digital platforms can enhance citizen engagement, promote digital inclusion, and strengthen government accountability. The findings will inform scalable, evidence-based digital governance solutions for municipal, national, and EU-wide implementation.

A Multidisciplinary International Consortium

The project brings together leading institutions from Belgium, Germany, Italy and Spain, ensuring technological, legal, and policy excellence. [Beyond the Horizon ISSG](#) leads coordination and policy expertise, supported by [Paderborn University](#) and [KU Leuven](#), which drive research on digital democracy and civic participation. [Deutsches Forschungszentrum für Künstliche Intelligenz \(DFKI\)](#) ensures AI-driven, secure digital governance solutions, while [Hybrid Core](#) develops the project's digital democracy app. [ICT Legal Consulting \(ICTLC\)](#) guarantees legal compliance, while [Trust-IT Services](#) and [COMMpla](#) contribute their expertise in digital communication and stakeholder engagement. Finally, [Fundación Cibervoluntarios](#) ensures the project remains focused on citizen inclusion and digital accessibility.

Collaborating for a Stronger Digital Democracy

INNOVADE is part of a wider European effort to make digital democracy more secure, inclusive and impactful. The project collaborates with its sister projects [AI4Deliberation](#) and [PERYCLES](#), funded under the same call, to ensure complementary research and maximise impact. As part of this effort, INNOVADE will co-host its **first webinar in March**, focusing on the challenges and needs of digital democracy. We

invite all those passionate about shaping the future of online civic participation to express their interest in joining us at [this form](#) and follow us for regular updates.

"Digital democracy must be inclusive, ethical, and practical," said Fatih Yilmaz, project coordinator from Beyond the Horizon ISSG. "With INNOVADE, we are ensuring that governments have state-of-the-art tools to make online participation not only work but work effectively for all citizens—not just the digitally savvy."

Get Involved

Policymakers, institutions, civil society organisations, and citizens are invited to engage with INNOVADE and help shape Europe's digital democracy future.

To stay updated on INNOVADE's progress, register for the newsletter at: <https://innovade-democracy.eu/>

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